

INTERACTIVE METHODS AND TECHNIQUES OF FORMING DUALITY IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the content of intellectual-active methods, innovative pedagogical technologies, and educational innovations and techniques that serve to make preschoolers bilingual in the educational process.*

Keywords: *educational innovations, blingism, innovation, pedagogical technology, interactive methods.*

INTRODUCTION

In today's developing educational process, the interest and attention to the use of interactive methods, innovative technologies, in the pedagogical process is increasing day by day. modern technologies teach them to independently study and analyze the acquired knowledge.

Interactive method - by increasing the activity between students and the teacher in the educational process, it serves to activate the learning of students and to develop their personal qualities. The use of interactive methods helps to increase the effectiveness of the lesson.

The main criteria of interactive education: conducting informal debates, the opportunity to freely describe and express the educational material, the number of lectures is small, but the number of seminars is large, the creation of opportunities for students to take initiative, small group, large group, class team assignment, writing assignments and other methods, which are of special importance in increasing the effectiveness of educational work.

Currently, one of the main directions in the field of improving educational methods is the introduction of interactive education and training methods. Teachers of all subjects are increasingly using interactive methods in the course of lessons.

As a result of the use of interactive methods, the students' skills of independent thinking, analysis, drawing conclusions, expressing their opinion, being able to defend it based on reasons, healthy communication, discussion, debate are formed and developed.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The concept of "innovative education" was first used in 1979 at the "Club of Rome". Innovative education (eng. "innovative"-innovation, invention) is a new idea, master, rule in the learner. Innovation differs from other innovations in that it has a variable mechanism that allows control and management. At the heart of innovation are new ideas, initiatives, non-traditional approaches, advanced work methods, specific goals aimed at changing the system. Innovation takes many forms.

Innovation is the creation of new technologies, the design of a new activity system for practice. Using innovative educational technologies, we apply a number of methods that serve to make students of junior school age bilingual.

Almost half of the world's population communicates using two languages. People who speak two languages are called bilinguals.

Bilingualism is a Latin word that means "two" and "lingua" means bilingualism. Bilinguals are people who communicate comfortably in one language. They are born with bilingualism based on family circumstances. Bilingual or people who have mastered two languages at the same time due to the current situation in the country. About 80 percent of the population of our country speak Uzbek. The remaining 20 percent consider dozens of other languages as their mother tongue. After Uzbek, the most widely spoken language is Russian. Uzbek Russian is widely used as a second language. In general education schools, English is taught as a second language from the 1st grade, and Russian is taught as a second language from the 2nd grade. In addition, French and German are also taught in schools.

Our country is Since it is an ethnic nation, there are schools that teach in Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Turkish, and Tajik languages. Children who study in such schools can speak Uzbek as well as the language of their own nation. Ignorance is an understatement. The need to learn a language is one of the most urgent issues of today. In order to bring our country into the ranks of developed countries, our level of knowledge should be sufficient. In today's globalized world, knowledge of foreign languages is of great importance in the formation of students as individuals. During the study of foreign languages, students acquire universal human values, the ability to analyze the environment and society, confidence to compete, respect for cultures and traditions, creativity, creativity and self-confidence in problematic situations and their country and people. and forms a sense of pride in its history. Therefore, the educational system of our country pays special attention to the teaching of Western and Eastern languages.

It is advisable to develop Bilingualism first in large groups of preschool educational institutions (5-6 years old), and in school from the 1st grade. Because there are scientific facts that a child should start learning a second language from the age of 5. Junior school We apply the innovative technologies used in the pedagogical process of learning a second language typical of students of the age of.

1. Innovative technology: USING MATCHES

This technology helps to acquire both practical and theoretical knowledge. The child expresses the new words he has learned based on shapes. We need a matchstick or a number of sticks for this. reads it aloud.

TARGET LANGUAGE: Vocabulary revision, spelling

RESOURCES: Matches (ten matches for each learner), the board, paper and pencils.

PREPARATION: Prepare a list of objects or animals the learners can make using matches.
TIME GUIDE: 10 minutes + for each activity

2. Innovative technology: Topic

This method is related to the formation of students' written speech and is aimed at the purposeful expression of thoughts related to the topic. In this, the student separates the text he wants to express in writing into meaningful parts and writes it. Sentence: My favorite meal is shashlik

reason: easy to cook

reason: fun to eat

reason: delicious

2. Sentence: Our school is the best in the city.

reason _____

reason _____ reason _____

3. Sentence: It is important to wear school uniform.

reason _____

reason _____ reason _____

3. Innovative technology: Find place

Let the learners play the game. Tell them to listen to a simple story, figure out which rooms you talk about and then put the clothes-pegs on the right boxes. The winner is the first person who puts pegs on all the rooms mentioned in the story.

For example:

A. It is Sunday morning. Everyone is at home. My brother is sleeping. My sister is having a bath. My mother is cooking lunch. My father is cutting the grass, and my grandma is watching TV.

Answers: bedroom, bathroom, kitchen, garden, living room...

B. One day I was looking for my teddy bear. First I looked under the bed. Next I checked the laundry basket next to the bath. Then I looked inside the cupboard where we keep sweets and chocolate. Last I looked under the big pillow on the sofa. Hurrah! My teddy bear was there.

Answers: bedroom, bathroom, kitchen, bedroom...

4. Innovative technology: Go on.

In this pedagogical technology, the teacher starts talking about a topic, and the students must be able to continue its logical continuation.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The educational technologies shown above were created on the basis of interesting games that are useful for elementary school students in learning a second language.

In the first matchstick method, the child develops both intellectual and physical development by using small hand motor skills. The second technology is aimed at forming writing skills. learns to show real reasons and to express his opinion freely.

The third method is aimed at developing listening skills, and correctly replaces the events in the story. it is necessary to find. With this method, the child learns to think logically. In the Go on method, the process that helps the child to compose a text, to think logically, and to enrich the world of imagination is reflected.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that language learning is a leading tool for knowing and understanding the world. The main goal of each method and technology is to provide a child with deep knowledge, update and enrich the educational process.

REFERENCES

1. A.A.Haydarov. “Tillar o’qitish metodikasi va ta’lim texnologiyalari”. 2016-y.
2. Azizxo’jayeva N.N.Pedagogik texnologiya va pedagogik mahorat.T.2003
[American Speech-Language-Hearing Association.](#)
3. Bialystok, Ellen, and Janet F. Werker. “The systematic effects of bilingualism on children’s development.” *Developmental science* 20.1 (2017).
4. Cromdal, J. (1999). Childhood bilingualism and metalinguistic skills: Analysis and control in young Swedish–English bilinguals. *Applied Psycholinguistics*, 20, 1–20.
5. Dijkstra, T. (2005). Bilingual visualword recognition and lexical access. In Kroll & de Groot (eds.), pp. 179–201.
6. ДАВЛЕТБАЕВА РАИСА ГУБАЙДУЛЛОВНА “МЕТОДИЧЕСКАЯ СИСТЕМА ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ БИЛИНГВАЛЬНОИЛИЧНОСТИ МЛАДШЕГО ШКОЛЬНИКА” Уфа-2010

7. Elen Bialystok Bilingualism in development Cambridge University PressOnline publication date: December 2009
8. Elen Bialystok BILINGUALISM IN DEVELOPMENTCambridge University Press 2001
9. Samarova, S. 2018. Forming Creative Vision of Person as Universal Method Enhancing Creativity.Eastern European Scientific Journal, 6.
10. Samarova, S. R. 2019. Methods and technologies for the development of creative thinking of pupils. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences, 710, 37-43.
11. Tojiyev M,Uralova M.Pedagogik texnoloyiya va pedagogik mahorat fanining o'quv mashg'ulotlarini loyhalash.O'quv qo'llanma T-."Tafakkur bo'stoni",2012
12. T.S.Sodiqov "Using Different Activities in English Classes"
13. Величковский Б.М. Психология познания и кибернетика // Кибернетика живого: человек в разных аспектах. - М.: Наука, 1985.-С. 92-106.
14. Padilla A.M. &Liebman E. Language Acquisition in the bilingual children // The Bilingual Review / La Revista Bilingue. - 1975. — Vol. 2. - Pp. 34-55.
15. Rasulova Istoda Abdulatifovna LINGVOMADANIY INTERFERENSIYA HAMDA UNI BARTARAF ETISH YO'L-YO'RIQLARI/ Samarqand – 2021.